

FINDING THE VOICE. BETWEEN LOCAL PRACTICE AND MEDIATED CANON IN SARDINIAN MULTIPART SINGING¹

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the role of audio recordings, particularly the 1995 recording *Sardegna. Confraternita delle Voci – Santu Lussurgiu* by Sardinia's vocal group Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu of Santu Lussurgiu, in the processes of transmission and canon formation of Sardinia's traditional multipart singing, known locally as cuncordu. It argues that this recording constitutes a shared musical canon, structured across sacred and secular repertoires, and based on specific vocal techniques and performance styles developed by the group over the years. Beginner singers commonly use the recording as a tool for individual practice, providing a repeatable sound model that anticipates their integration into the collective performance context. The analysis draws on the concept of canon in folk music and the theory of mediatization of oral traditions, highlighting the transformation of musical knowledge from oral community practice into a partially mediated process. The article concludes by situating the recording's release within its local historical and cultural context, underlining its role in formalizing and disseminating the *cuncordu* repertoire of Santu Lussurgiu, while also discussing the role of ethnomusicology in the processes of mediation and transmission of the musical cultures it studies.

Alla ricerca della voce. Pratiche locali e canoni mediati nel canto a più voci della Sardegna. Questo articolo esamina i processi di mediatizzazione nella musica di tradizione orale della Sardegna attraverso l'analisi delle registrazioni audio e del loro ruolo nella trasmissione del canto a cuncordu, con particolare riferimento all'album del 1995 *Sardegna. Confraternita delle Voci – Santu Lussurgiu* del gruppo Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu. L'articolo sostiene che questa registrazione abbia agito come un dispositivo centrale nella riorganizzazione delle pratiche di apprendimento e di trasmissione, offrendo ai cantori un modello sonoro stabile e riproducibile che affianca e, in alcuni casi, anticipa l'esperienza performativa diretta. Nel tempo, tale supporto registrato ha contribuito alla sedimentazione di specifiche tecniche vocali e modalità esecutive sviluppate dal gruppo. L'analisi si sviluppa a partire da una riflessione sul concetto di canone in ambito musicale e sulle teorie della mediazione delle tradizioni orali, mettendo in luce il passaggio dalla trasmissione basata sull'esperienza comunitaria diretta a forme di conoscenza sempre più articolate attraverso supporti registrati. L'articolo si conclude collocando la pubblicazione della registrazione nel suo specifico contesto storico e culturale, evidenziandone il ruolo nella formalizzazione e nella circolazione del repertorio del cuncordu di Santu Lussurgiu e discutendo sul ruolo dell'etnomusicologia nei processi di mediazione e trasmissione delle culture musicali che studia.

¹ This article draws on material from Chapter 5 of the author's PhD dissertation in Ethnomusicology, *For the Village, For the Music: Exploring Identity in Sardinian Multipart Singing between Oral Tradition and Popular Culture* (Memorial University of Newfoundland), presently under final review.

A FAMILY MEMOIR

On Thursday afternoon of the first day of spring 2008, I was at my parents' house in Santu Lussurgiu, my home village, enjoying a good chat about music with my nephew, Antonio. At that time, he was fourteen years old and was opening up to me about his interest in starting to sing *cuncordu*. He listened to traditional performances multiple times but never tried to sing one of the four vocal parts and wanted to ask me some advice on how to choose one that he could start learning.

It was not the case that we were talking coincidentally on that day. That Thursday was the day before Easter, a day when the village celebrates the traditional procession of *s'Incravamentu* (Sardinian for "the nailing"), the para-liturgical representation of the crucifixion that is staged by four different religious confraternities and followed by the entire Santu Lussurgiu community. We were both thinking about following the evening procession, watching the statue of the crucified Christ being carried by the confraternity members from one church to another, and, above all, listening to the *Miserere* and the *Novena*, the two songs sung by a four-part singing group during the ritual.² I was well acquainted with the practice, having been a member of the Rosariu confraternity in my youth. For some time, I had also attempted (with modest results) to perform one of the parts, the highest one, known as the *contraltu*. Antonio was amazed by the rituals of Holy Week, particularly because of his love for the multipart singing. Of the four parts, he liked the *contra* the most. After chatting about the peculiarities of the *contra*'s vocal role (its low frequencies and cavernous timbre) and referring to esteemed *contra* singers of the village, Antonio tried to "do this voice," approaching the *contra* part and following its motion in a song.

Singing together, we overcame the critical problem of having only two people (you need four voices to sing *cuncordu*) with the help of recordings. We went into my bedroom, I searched my bookshelf for a CD, found it, and inserted it into my little hi-fi stereo. The disc, titled *Sardegna. Confraternita delle voci – Santu Lussurgiu* was recorded in 1995 by the Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu, the most respected *cuncordu* group of the village. As it happens in many other villages, *cuncordu* is the term used in Santu Lussurgiu, which is my hometown, to refer to the local traditional multipart singing, sung by four voices, *bassu*, *contra*, *'oghe*, and *contraltu*. This musical style finds its most significant expression during the Catholic paraliturgical rites of the Holy Week, celebrated by the four local religious confraternities. On Maundy Thursday and Good Friday, the *cuncordu* of the Cunfraria 'e su Rosariu (Confraternity of the Rosary), the same group that every year since 1975 has been deputed to accompany the Holy Week rituals with its singing, represents the musical link between the community and the sacred realm.

As soon as I pressed the play button, the room was filled with the sounds of the *bassu* part voicing the first Latin lines of the *Miserere*. We listened to this first solo part, waiting for the entrance of the other three voices and then listened specifically to the *contra*,

² Literally the *novena* in Sardinian. While the term typically refers to a nine-day cycle of Catholic devotional prayers and rituals, in this context the term does not denote this liturgical sequence. Instead, *novena* serves as a proper name for the chant, possibly evoking devotional or religious associations without a direct link to the traditional nine-day practice.

which Antonio was willing to learn. We stopped the track after a while and tried to replicate the exact timbre performed by the voice. Even if the part that I usually sing is the *cuntraltu* (the highest part of the group, which in other towns is called the *mesa boghe*), I was able to find the *contra* part and help Antonio follow it. We sang the vocal part together, pressed play again, waited for the *contra* entrance, and sang over the recording. We pressed stop, tried another time, and then again. We repeated this process several times, and I stopped singing soon after. Antonio was eventually able to produce the *contra* timbre ideally. He had just found his voice. We celebrated the moment a little bit, and then I removed the CD from the hi-fi, inserted it into its plastic sleeve, and handed it to Antonio. From now on, he would have the ability to experiment with finding his voice by himself, in the private environment of his bedroom, listening not only to the *Miserere* but to all religious and secular repertoire of *cuncordu* singing, all comprised in the track list of this CD, which serves to summarize the entire local tradition.

Before encountering any first attempt to sing in public contexts and with other singers, the recordings made by the Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu would offer a virtual school, frozen in time, that could be repeated and broken up into fragments thanks to the play, stop, and pause controls. But how much do such recordings influence the learning process of new singers? How significantly does it impact an oral tradition like *cuncordu* singing in Santu Lussurgiu? To what extent do such recordings shape emerging practices and aesthetic expectations? Furthermore, how do they intersect with existing hierarchies of legitimacy within the community? What happens when recordings circulate within a community that maintains a strong continuity of practice? Can recorded media still foster renewal, or do they primarily reinforce existing hierarchies and stylistic norms?

This article explores the complex interplay between media, canon formation, and oral transmission in the multipart singing tradition of Santu Lussurgiu. It opens with an analysis of the 1995 CD by the Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu, a landmark recording that affirms a well-established sacred and secular repertoire and functions as a foundational learning tool for aspiring singers.³ From there, the article broadens its scope to consider the broader media landscape surrounding the tradition (including audio recordings, books, and documentary films) and examines the central role that Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu has played in shaping the aesthetic and pedagogical standards of *cuncordu* singing. These dynamics cannot be separated from the long-standing and sometimes ambivalent relationship between the singers of Santu Lussurgiu and Italian ethnomusicologists, whose research and documentation have contributed significantly to how the tradition is transmitted and perceived.

³ In Sardinian, *su* is the singular masculine definite article, *sa* is the singular feminine definite article, *sos* is the plural masculine definite article, and *sas* is the plural feminine definite article.

CANONS, REPERTOIRES, AND RECORDINGS

In his 1998 book, *The Study of Folk Music in the Modern World*, ethnomusicologist Philip Bohlman devotes a chapter to folk music canons. For Bohlman, a community shapes specific forms of musical behavior and repertoires to distinguish itself as a social entity. Canon formation is an ongoing process that responds creatively to new contexts and texts (1998: 104). Establishing a canon encapsulates the community's aesthetic decisions and the internal motivation for cultural expression, displaying a selection of the characteristics that will compose the community's cultural repertoire, which is always affected by internal and external influences. Bohlman labels the decisions that form musical canons as "socially motivated", linking these to the community's social values related to a particular historical context. This includes conceptualizing folk music made by the community in the past and how these social and cultural values are represented in the present. Following this line of thought, Bohlman argues that canon formation is connected to cultural processes like the origins of repertoires, the musician's roles in their society, the music classification system of the community, its aesthetics, and the technical expectations involved in folk music (1998: 105).

The canon-formation processes «result from a community's transformation of cultural values into aesthetic expression» (Bohlman 1998: 106) and are always pragmatically connected to its ideas about the flexibility of cultural contexts of the modern world. Here, the inscription of cultural meaning in a canon is related to resonant musical symbols. If a musical tradition gains supporters, they will accept this system of symbols as representative of a community, which is the central context of all musical decisions (1998: 109). Bohlman discusses different types of canon formations, which vary depending on the size of the community involved. The first of these, which interests me in this article, is the "small group" canon, in which everyone in the community knows everyone else, at least in theory. For Bohlman, canon formation in small groups is related to a strong sense of belonging in a traditional setting (1998: 111). Here, many community members «know at least a representative sample of the group's shared repertory» (1998: 112), which can be passed on through traditional settings for oral transmission or conveyed through modern forms of mediation, like sound recordings.

Canon formation is distinct from but related to the notion of repertoire, which is the subject of folklorist Neil Rosenberg's 2002 article that examines the work of Canadian fiddler Don Messer. Rosenberg examines how documents, recordings, and lists of songs can function simultaneously as aids to performance and as artifacts of tradition, highlighting the interplay between oral practice and mediated forms (2002: 194-95). The repertoire is continually renewed through performance, yet live renditions are not the only factors shaping its formation. The reproducibility of recorded sound has made recordings a crucial element in establishing a repertoire. The possibilities inherent in recorded music have not only transformed how repertoires are created but also altered their modes of circulation, the processes of distribution, the ways people listen, and, in many cases, the methods through which musical traditions are taught. Records contribute to «a selectively constructed canon» (Rosenberg 2002: 204) contained in the recorded repertoire, which is mediated, categorized, and labeled by a community of

musicians and audiences (Diamond 2011: 11). Unlike repertoires that are only formed in live music, mediated repertoires can be repeated endlessly through their recorded form.

Bohlman (1998) also discusses the role of media technologies in the institutionalization of folk music canons. Historically, the printing of sheet music and, later, the development of audio recordings offered the ground for consolidating traditional repertoires. In some contexts, recording technology provided the means of maintaining entire music traditions (1998: 65). Moreover, recordings played «a vital role in the technologizing of oral tradition: musicians commonly learn new pieces directly from a record or tape cassette» (1998: 66). Forming a canon and establishing a repertoire take on mediatized contours as oral traditions become embedded in the historical practices of recording and circulation. Here, the voice or instruments are separated from the performer's body and acquire «a nearly autonomous cultural dimension» (Scaldaferri 2014: 18), creating a new range of meaning and values profoundly related to its mediation through its recording.

Dan Lundberg, Krister Malm, and Owe Ronström (2003) offer a critical lens through which to examine the impact of recording technologies on oral music traditions. Building on earlier work by Wallis and Malm (1984), the authors define mediatization as adapting musical forms to the constraints and possibilities of media formats and markets. In particular, Wallis and Malm introduce the notion of “primary mediaization”⁴ (1984: 70) whereby the first recording of a repertoire transforms how the music of that repertoire circulates and the pedagogical practices of its tradition. In this framework, recorded music not only documents but also teaches and standardizes, allowing high-status musicians to establish authoritative models that others learn from and emulate – thus reshaping oral traditions from within.

The relationship between canon creation and recording technology has been central to transmitting the multipart singing repertoire in Santu Lussurgiu. Here, mediaization allowed the reification of specific values from the oral tradition associated with the music of the village's religious confraternities. My interest here lies in how recordings construct a representation of a village's body of works, and how the act of listening – understood as the «momentary performance of an intentional act» (Anderson 2004: 6) – reinforces these representations, linking the listener to a repertoire established by recording artists as emblematic of a community of singers and, more broadly, of the village itself. I will show how recordings act as a tool for beginners to learn the tradition in Santu Lussurgiu. I will also focus on how these recordings act as a primary mediated pedagogic tool for beginners.

⁴ The authors intentionally use the term “mediaization” rather than mediatization to emphasize the material and technological processes through which music is shaped by media systems.

A VILLAGE, ITS MUSIC, ITS SINGERS

Santu Lussurgiu, located on the southeastern slopes of the Montiferru range in central-western Sardinia, is a mountain village surrounded by oak and chestnut forests and fed by natural springs. Its medieval urban layout – narrow cobbled streets, stone houses, and prominent churches such as San Pietro and the late-Gothic Santa Maria degli Angeli – reflects a long-standing cultural and spiritual heritage (Mele 2005). Historically a center of anti-feudal activism, it gained prominence in the late 18th century for supporting Giovanni Maria Angioy's revolutionary movement (Cherchi-Paba 1969) and later became a hub for education and regional culture, hosting figures such as Antonio Gramsci in the early 1900s (Gramsci 1979). The village's economy traditionally combined agriculture, pastoralism, and artisanal crafts, particularly saddlery and leatherwork, which remain celebrated today. The population has declined in recent decades due to post-war emigration (Pau 2002). Nevertheless, heritage-based tourism has also revived, including the "albergo diffuso" model, which integrates historic buildings into hospitality infrastructure.

Santu Lussurgiu's festive calendar is anchored by two significant events: *sa Carrela 'e Nanti* (literally, the road in the front), a daring carnival horse race, and the *Chida Santa* (Holy Week), a solemn religious cycle organized by four confraternities with origins in the 16th and 17th centuries (Corona 2011, 2015). At the heart of these traditions lies *cuncordu*, the local form of Sardinian multipart singing, based on the full sonority of the major triad in root position and performed by four male voices named, from the lowest to the highest, *bassu*, *contra*, *'oghe*, and *cuntraltu*. Typically sung in close physical formation, with an upright and contained posture, *cuncordu* embodies solemnity and precision. Sacred singing – primarily related to the sonic accompaniment of the Holy Week rituals – is widely regarded as the most prestigious expression of the tradition, yet secular performance – often heard during community get-togethers (like the ones related to carnival), village festivals, informal gatherings in private wine cellars – retains equal cultural importance (Macchiarella 2017). Songs draw on fixed melodic, harmonic, and rhythmic structures, with lyrics in Sardu and, in some sacred contexts, in Latin. Today, *cuncordu* remains the most practiced musical form in Santu Lussurgiu, connecting generations through shared repertoire, performance discipline, and a profound sense of communal belonging.

In Santu Lussurgiu, the sacred *cuncordu* repertoire is divided into two main categories. The first includes the *Miserere* and the *Novena*, performed exclusively during Holy Week by *cuncordos* formally affiliated with the village's four confraternities. The *Miserere*, sung in Latin, carries an aura of solemn mystery, while the *Novena*, sung in Sardinian, offers an intimate lament of the Virgin Mary's sorrow, its immediacy accessible to all. Selection of singers for these pieces follows long-standing confraternal protocols, and participation is considered the highest musical and symbolic distinction in the tradition. Strictly reserved for the Holy Week rites – happening on Holy Tuesday, Maundy Thursday, and Good Friday – their performance is bound by a deeply internalized ethos of religious propriety.

The *Miserere* is regarded as the most technically demanding and spiritually elevated piece, drawing on a condensed local version of Psalm 50 that has been transmitted orally

for generations. Mastery is judged not only by vocal precision but also by adherence to a shared aesthetic standard recognized by both singers and knowledgeable non-performing listeners. The *Novena*, by contrast, brings the Passion's human dimension to the fore, its slow tempo and measured silences enhancing the poetic imagery of Mary's grief, particularly during *s'Ispravamentu*, the ritual deposition from the Cross (Macchiarella 2009).

The second category of sacred repertoire includes settings of the *Ordinarium Missae* (excluding the *Credo*) and other religious songs, such as *su Ninniu*, *su Perdonu*, *Deus te salvet Maria*, and *sos Gosos*. While often linked to specific confraternities, these pieces may be performed more freely by any skilled *cuncordu*. *Sos Gosos* – devotional hymns in Sardinian praising the Virgin or the saints – are especially significant as both liturgical expressions and affirmations of confraternal identity (Mele 2017). Together, these repertoires articulate the spiritual life of the village, sustaining a balance between formal ritual authority and broader community participation.

Alongside its central role in Holy Week and confraternity life, *cuncordu* in Santu Lussurgiu thrives in secular contexts that foster spontaneity, conviviality, and humor (Macchiarella 2009: 112-113). Unlike the sacred repertoire, which is primarily restricted to confraternal groups, secular songs are accessible to all singers, including ad hoc quartets formed during social gatherings.

The most emblematic example is *s'Istudiantina* (the student song), performed especially during convivial gatherings. Flexible in structure, it accommodates verses drawn from Sardinian poetry or oral tradition and is sung by dozens of villagers (*ibid.*: 76-79). Other notable pieces include *sa Pastorina* (the shepherd's song), whose pastoral imagery, two-chord harmonic motion, and vocables suggest a historical link with throat-articulated singing still present in nearby villages. *S'Acchettuzzedda* (the young mare) offers a humorous, parodic take on local equestrian culture. At the same time, *s'Amorada* (the lover) – based on Paolicu Mossa's poem *Sa bellezza de Clori* (the beauty of Clori) – follows a fixed poetic and musical format.⁵ The technically demanding *Ottava Trista* (the sad octave), thematically rooted in lost love and poetic idealization, is valued for its interpretive richness and melodic structure, which weaves together segments from sacred chants such as the *Miserere* and the *Novena*, reconfigured into a distinctive secular song. It is widely regarded among local singers as one of the most technically and expressively demanding pieces in the repertoire. As with the *Ottava Trista*, performance boundaries between sacred and secular have historically been fluid. Local singers recall recasting sacred texts within secular melodies or vice versa as strategies to navigate contextual constraints. While the *Miserere* remains strictly tied to its liturgical setting, pieces like the *Novena* have occasionally migrated beyond Holy Week, acquiring new meanings in community life through secular texts.

⁵ Paolo (Paulicu) Mossa (1821-1892) was one of the most important Sardinian-language poets of the nineteenth century.

SU CUNCORDU 'E SU ROSARIU

The tradition of multipart singing in Santu Lussurgiu is deeply rooted in the village's religious and social institutions, particularly in the lay confraternities (*cunfrarias*) that have historically governed much of the ritual and communal life. Dating back to the sixteenth and seventeenth centuries, the confraternities serve as key custodians of sacred song and ceremony. Beyond their liturgical purposes, the confraternities function as custodians of communal Christian values and guardians of intangible heritage, preserving the aesthetics, performance practices, and repertoires of *cuncordu* singing. Their influence extends across the religious calendar, and their internal hierarchies shape the organization of rituals and the transmission of vocal roles and techniques (Macchiarella 2017).⁶ The *Cunfraria 'e su Rosariu* (confraternity of the Rosary) holds a privileged position among these confraternities. It is entrusted with organizing the most solemn rites of Holy Week and selecting the quartet that will perform *su Miserere* and *sa Novena*. The ensemble that arises from this confraternity, known as *Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu* (literally, the *cuncordu* of the Rosariu confraternity), is regarded by the community as the principal authority on the sacred repertoire. Since the late 1970s, this group has been consistently chosen to sing during the Holy Thursday and Good Friday rituals, further consolidating its central role in the ritual life of the village.⁷

Through decades of rigorous practice, participation in rites, and engagement with ethnomusicological researchers and other musicians, *Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu* has established a performance model that most singers in the village reference. Founded in 1975, the group has had the same members for over four decades, embodying a form of continuity in Sardinian multipart singing.

Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu is composed of Antonio Migheli (b. 1951, *'oghe*), Mario Corona (b. 1952, *contra*), Roberto Iriu (b. 1959, *cuntraltu*), and Giovanni Ardu (1952–2020, *bassu*). The group began their journey when interest in traditional sacred singing was waning: many elder singers were abandoning active participation in *cuncordu* music, and the transmission of knowledge about the tradition was increasingly precarious. Against this backdrop of cultural fragility, the young members of *Su Cuncordu* took it upon themselves to revitalize the practice. Motivated by a strong sense of communal duty and devotional commitment, they began singing to ensure that the rituals of Holy Week – particularly *s'Incravamentu* and *s'Isravamentu* – would continue to be accompanied by the musical forms tradition prescribed. In interviews conducted during my fieldwork, all four original members of *Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu* recalled that during their first year

⁶ Beyond the confraternities, other kinds of quartets can be found in the village. These latter operate independently of confraternal structures. Though these groups are as committed to the stylistic integrity of local traditions as those of the confraternities, they focus primarily on the secular repertoire and are not called upon to participate in Holy Week rites or other liturgical performances. However, they also perform in other religious contexts, like singing the *Missa* (mass) weddings or patron saint festivals.

⁷ In addition to the *Rosariu*, two other confraternities play significant musical roles during Holy Week in Santu Lussurgiu. The *Santa Rughe* confraternity leads the singing during *su Nazarenu* on Holy Tuesday, performing the *Miserere* and *sa Novena* in the Church of Santa Croce. The *Sette Dolores* confraternity provides performances of selected *Novena* stanzas during the *settenario* (the seven-day vigil leading up to the Holy Week; see Regione Autonoma della Sardegna 2020).

participating in the Holy Week rites, they organized themselves into a *cuncordu* in haste, moved by the shared conviction that *non che leare Deus a sa muda* (Christ wouldn't be left in silence). At the time, they knew only a single stanza of the Miserere and one of the Novena, which they performed to provide at least a minimal sonic presence within the rite. The following is an excerpt of my interview with Mario Corona, the *contra* from Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu:

In '76, I came back to hear the Holy Tuesday procession. I remember it well – it was Holy Tuesday – I came to hear the choir that was supposed to walk through the village streets, as was customary. However, there was no one. The choir had not been formed. Holy Tuesday, and no choir? There wasn't one. I often sang a few songs here and there with a dear friend, Giovanni Ardu – may he rest in peace – but we did it informally, without any particular ambition.⁸ However, by Thursday afternoon, no one was deputed to sing. So we formed a choir, just so that 'Christ would not be left in silence,' as they say – it would have been shameful to have no singing in the *Incravamentu* procession (interview with Mario Corona, March 17, 2023).⁹

Born from a sense of urgency, Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu has become a long-standing project committed to cultural revitalization. Its members have been dedicated to learning the music from the few elder singers that were still alive, absorbing styles, gestures, and vocal practices through listening to them singing and interviewing them. Further, the group has engaged in extensive archival research, seeking out old reel-to-reel tapes, fragments of early recordings, and testimonies from villagers to recover a repertoire that had already begun to dissolve. A powerful example of this process is their work on *s'Ottava Trista*. A low-quality reel-to-reel recording of the song was made in the 1960s by a local group of *cuncordu* elders. The recording circulated informally for many years, and while the piece was still in oral memory in the late 1970s, it was no longer sung in public at that time. The quartet reconstructed the piece by carefully reworking the performance captured on that degraded reel. Through their effort, the song re-entered the village's collective body of works, albeit in a form that bore the interpretive signature of Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu (Macchiarella 2009: 88).

Since the late 1970s, Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu has had a central role in the rites of Holy Week, singing during Maundy Thursday *s'Incravamentu* (the nailing) and Good Friday *s'Isravamentu* (the unnauling) each year until 2019. Their performances established a sonic standard for sacred multipart singing in the village. Over time, the four members came to be regarded as cultural custodians whose knowledge and stylistic authority serve as reference points for other singers, locally and beyond. At the same

⁸ An analogous account was also collected by Ignazio Macchiarella. See Macchiarella 2009: 137.

⁹ [Nel 76, sono rientrato per sentire il Martedì Santo. Mi ricordo bene, era il Martedì Santo, per sentire un po' il coro che sarebbe dovuto andare lungo le strade del Paese come si usava. Non c'era nessuno. Il coro non era stato formato. Come Martedì Santo e non c'è il coro? Non c'era proprio il coro. Io molte volte avevo accennato dei canti con un nostro amico buonanima, Giovanni Ardu, e facevamo dei canti così, alla spicciolata, senza nessuna pretesa. E comunque il giovedì, il giovedì pomeriggio, non c'era ancora nessuno. E abbiamo fatto un coro, un coro per non che du leare a sa muda come si dice, sarebbe stato vergognoso senza il canto nella processione de *s'Incravamentu*.]

time, their reputation extends far beyond the boundaries of Santu Lussurgiu. While remaining deeply rooted in their confraternal obligations and the sacred calendar, from the early eighties Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu progressively began to tour nationally and internationally, bringing the Lussurgese tradition to stages and audiences unconnected to the ritual context from which it emerged.

FIG. 1. Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu singing during the 2016 Holy Week rituals. Photo by Diego Pani.

Starting in the 1980s, Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu, and the *cuncordu* practice in general, have attracted growing interest from Italian ethnomusicologists. Before turning to the more recent scholarly engagement with Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu, it is useful to briefly outline the earlier history of discographic documentation of Sardinian multipart singing, which laid the groundwork for later institutional and ethnomusicological attention. The discographic history of the genre – especially in its religious and confraternal expressions – must be situated within the broader trajectory of sound documentation and phonographic publication in Sardinia, where chest-voice singing linked to confraternities often entered circulation through ethnomusicological fieldwork and editorial projects carried forward primarily by researchers.

Compared to the rich corpus of recordings of throat-articulated singing broadly known as *tenore*, the history of recordings of chest-voice singing associated with the religious sphere and commonly known as *cuncordu* has remained more limited and received less attention. While the vocal practices of the more “secular” *tenore* singing began to circulate widely through commercial recordings as early as the 1960s, the documentation of confraternal *cuncordu* singing traditions evolved slowly, often tied to specific

ethnomusicological projects. The earliest significant attempt to capture Sardinian religious polyphony dates to the 1920s, when Gavino Gabriel recorded in the village of Aggius (Gabriel 1910; Lutz 2019). In 1948, the town of Bosa hosted one of RAI's pioneering 45rpm releases. It included sacred and secular content, notably featuring a young boy interpreting a religious chant. Throughout the 1960s, commercial interest in Sardinian traditional music began to grow modestly, with LPs such as *Bosa il Mentigada / Sardigna Modesta* (Forgotten Bosa / Modest Sardinia; see Coro di Bosa 1960) offering one of the first vinyl recordings of sacred multipart singing from Bosa. Around the same time, ethnomusicologist Giorgio Nataletti was conducting extensive field recordings throughout Sardinia for the Centro Nazionale di Studi di Musica Popolare (CNSMP, national center for the study of traditional music). His work documented a broad range of vocal practices – including confraternal and multipart singing traditions, like the ones of the town of Aggius – as part of a national ethnographic archive project sponsored by RAI (Lutz 2015). During the same years, a key figure in the documentation of Sardinian multipart singing for broadcast purposes was the archaeologist Ovidio Addis, who in 1956 carried out a series of field recordings in communities such as Seneghe, Santu Lussurgiu, Aidomaggiore, Bosa, and Cuglieri. These sessions, likely conducted with technical support from the regional RAI offices, focused on both sacred and secular multipart singing repertoires.¹⁰ A turning point in the recording history came with the *Musica Sarda* LP box-set (1973), edited by Diego Carpitella, Pietro Sassu, and Leonardo Sole.¹¹ The collection, among other Sardinian traditional music, assembled field recordings from diverse singing traditions, including the villages Aggius, Castelsardo, and Cheremule, and provided broader visibility to Sardinian multipart singing. In 1985, the cassette *Su Coro Antigu de Bosa* (the old choir of Bosa), issued by the label Tirso, became the first recording focused entirely on a single vocal group and its sacred and secular repertoires (Su Coru Antigu de Bosa 1985).¹²

As we have seen, sacred bodies of work have received less attention than secular ones in the history of traditional music recording projects in Sardinia, and the music of Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu has played a key role in validating this marginalized genre. Their first credited recording occurred in 1987 on the LP box set *Canti liturgici di tradizione orale*, which was curated by Piero Arcangeli, Roberto Leydi, Renato Morelli, and Pietro Sassu. Released by the Milan-based Albatros label and featuring examples of oral liturgical traditions from across Italy, the disc brought the group to the attention of scholars of vernacular sacred music from across Italy and placed their work in the

¹⁰ Addis would later draw on this material for a three-part radio series aired in 1964 on Radio Sardegna, contributing to the mediated dissemination of *cantu a cuncordu* at a time when such traditions were largely absent from the public media sphere. On the presence of Sardinian traditional music in regional broadcasting and the role of figures such as Addis in these early efforts, see Milleddu 2021.

¹¹ *Musica Sarda* was published both as a box set containing three LPs and as three separate LPs. The individual records featured different cover artwork and did not include the booklet that accompanied the original box set edition.

¹² The full name of this group was Su Coru Antigu de Bosa "Agoroppamentu Pranarza", that can be translated as the old choir of bosa "Pranarza group". Pranarza is the geographical region where the town of Bosa is located.

broader, if still modest, history of Sardinian confraternal music recordings.¹³ The inclusion of *Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu* in *Canti Liturgici di Tradizione Orale* was thus a pivotal moment in recognizing and institutionalizing Sardinian religious multipart singing in the broader field of Italian ethnomusicology.

FIG. 2. Mario Corona's own copy of the *Canti Liturgici di Tradizione Orale* box set. Photo by Diego Pani.

This recording was the culmination of a project that grew out of two live sets of events: the 1984 festival *Autunno Musicale di Como* (Como autumn music festival) and two concerts produced in Venice in 1985 for the *Anno Europeo della Musica* (European year of music).¹⁴ These concerts were the first time *Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu* performed

¹³ Based in Milan and directed by Italian ethnomusicologist Roberto Leydi, the Albatros label played a pivotal role in the Italian folk music revival of the 1970s. Emerging in a period of renewed interest in regional musical traditions and politically engaged ethnographic research, the label was committed to publishing previously unreleased field recordings and distributing licensed works from international sources, such as Folkways Records. Its mission was not merely archival but also pedagogical and political, aiming to celebrate subaltern musical cultures. Each LP was typically accompanied by extensive scholarly liner notes. The label's catalog stands today as one of the most important repositories of vernacular and folk music published in Italy during the 20th century (De Luigi 2008).

¹⁴ The initiative began in 1983 and 1984 with the *Autunno Musicale di Como*, where singers from various regions – including Santu Lussurgiu, Aggius, Latera, and Sessa Aurunca – were invited to perform paraliturgical repertoires as part of a broader ethnomusicological project aimed at documenting oral liturgical traditions across Italy. In anticipation of the 1985 *Anno Europeo della Musica*, the Società Italiana di Etnomusicologia (SIE) launched a coordinated national survey of orally transmitted liturgical and paraliturgical music, mobilizing a wide network of scholars and fieldworkers. The project led to a scholarly

outside Sardinia. Two of the most influential figures in Italian ethnomusicology facilitated the ensemble's inclusion in these concerts, Roberto Leydi (1928-2003) and Pietro Sassu (1939-2001). Along with ethnomusicologist Renato Morelli, both Leydi and Sassu were instrumental in conceptualizing and implementing these events, which led to the *Musica e liturgia* project. One of the founders of modern Italian ethnomusicology, Leydi served as a scientific advisor to the *Autunno Musicale di Como* festival. Pietro Sassu, one of the three editors of the seminal *Musica Sarda* box set (1973), was a pivotal encounter for Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu. Trained in classical music and paleography, he was a key figure in Italian ethnomusicology. He began fieldwork in Sardinia in the early 1960s, focusing extensively on multipart singing, conducting, among other villages, research in Santu Lussurgiu since 1973. Sassu maintained a close relationship with the newly formed Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu, recorded their early performances, and supported their performances outside the village. For Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu, participation in this initiative marked a significant turning point. Several group members have identified their performance at the Como festival as the beginning of their artistic journey beyond the boundaries of Santu Lussurgiu. Their involvement in this project expanded their visibility, giving them institutional legitimacy and academic recognition. The live events and the recording that came out of them helped to form the canon of traditional sacred music in Italy, crystallizing a specific image of Sardinian devotional polyphony that would inform writings in ethnomusicology and discourses about musical heritage.¹⁵ The collaboration between these researchers and the group continued in 1988 with the production of the RAI documentary *Su Concordu*, directed by Renato Morelli and with scientific supervision by Sassu.¹⁶ It offered a detailed portrayal of Holy Week in Santu Lussurgiu, focusing particularly on ritual actions and the practice of sacred singing. The film was produced by Italy's national public broadcaster and benefited from wide distribution. For several years, it was broadcast on national television during the days preceding Easter, providing Su Cuncordu and the Rosariu confraternity with significant media exposure.

Sassu's collaboration with Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu continued in other initiatives, including the 1991 conference *Liturgia e Paraliturgia nella Tradizione Orale* (Liturgy and paraliturgical practice in oral tradition), which Pietro Sassu and the local musicologist Giampaolo Mele curated.¹⁷ In addition to academic papers, the conference featured

conference and two concerts at the Teatro La Fenice in Venice. Recordings from the Como and Venice concerts comprised the tracks of the *Canti Liturgici di Tradizione Orale* box set, which included extensive liner notes. Notably, the box set was an attempt to represent the broad range of traditional sacred music in Italy (Morelli 2017).

¹⁵ *Canti Liturgici di Tradizione Orale* was republished by Nota in 2011 in the Geos CD Book series. The reissue consists of a book of 155 pages with 3 audio CDs and over 50 tracks. Importantly, the original sound recordings have been digitally remastered in this edition.

¹⁶ Spelling the name of the genre "concordu," rather than "cuncordu," the title of the documentary is meant to represent the way that this word is sometimes pronounced in Santu Lussurgiu.

¹⁷ Giampaolo Mele is Associate Professor of Medieval and Renaissance Music History at the University of Sassari, where he teaches in both the undergraduate and graduate programs in Literary and Communication Sciences. He has also taught medieval church history, Latin paleography, and musical paleography. See Mele 2005, 2017.

evening concerts with singing groups from all of Sardinia, which were organized by Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu and hosted in Santu Lussurgiu by the Centro di Cultura Popolare UNLA, the village's principal cultural institution.¹⁸ In interviews, the singers in the group depict the conference as a pivotal event in their careers and the broader history of Italian ethnomusicology. The gathering attracted the most prominent scholars of the time, including key figures like Roberto Leydi and many young students who became established scholars in Italian ethnomusicology like Ignazio Macchiarella, Maurizio Agamennone, and Francesco Giannattasio. In both the interviews I conducted with him and his books on the history of the Rosariu confraternity (2011, 2015), Corona affectionately refers to the conference participants as "quelli del '91" (those from '91). This moment is perceived as one of profound recognition. The singers were not only involved as performers but also took on an active role in organizing the conference. Their inclusion in this context is remembered with pride and continues to nourish a sense of intellectual and cultural legitimacy.¹⁹

FIG. 3. Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu during the shootings of *Su Concordu* documentary (1988). Photo by Giuseppe Firinu.

¹⁸ Founded in 1947, the UNLA (Unione Nazionale per la Lotta contro l'Analfabetismo; National union for the fight against illiteracy) was a federal institution that sought to eradicate illiteracy and promote civic education in rural and marginalized areas of Italy. Following World War II, UNLA established Centri di Cultura Popolare (Popular culture centers) across the country, particularly in southern regions and the islands, including Sardinia. These centers operate as local hubs for adult literacy, cultural education, and civic development, often in collaboration with local teachers, intellectuals, and municipal authorities. In towns like Santu Lussurgiu, the Centro UNLA became a key institution not only for literacy campaigns but also for the documentation and transmission of local cultural heritage, including music and other oral traditions.

¹⁹ The publication of the conference proceedings – *Liturgia e Paraliturgia nella Tradizione Orale* (Sassu and Mele 1993) – has been cited by the singers as a cornerstone in the literature. Frequently mentioned in interviews and conversations, the book is seen as an authoritative source, one that is still consulted for educational and documentary purposes.

The 1991 conference involved another important figure in the career of Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu. A primary schoolteacher by profession, as well as an ethnographer and museum curator, Francesco Salis (1923-2007) was a prominent intellectual from Santu Lussurgiu.²⁰ Starting in the mid-1980s, he served as a crucial facilitator and coordinator for the group, responding to invitations for performances outside the village, accompanying them on their early national and international tours, and frequently introducing their concerts. During this time, their live performances became more frequent, with appearances at scholarly conferences, major world music festivals, and international tours. All of this raised the awareness of the *cuncordu* tradition outside of Sardinia. This increased visibility led to even more invitations, resulting in performances in prestigious European theaters, abbeys, and concert halls that positioned the group within broader artistic networks that bridged traditional, jazz, and contemporary music.

During this time, Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu began to collaborate with influential figures in the Italian and Sardinian music scenes, including Maria Carta, a leading voice in Sardinian folk revival; Luigi Cinque, a composer and multi-instrumentalist known for fusing Mediterranean musical styles with jazz and other improvised musics; and Paolo Fresu, the internationally acclaimed Sardinian jazz trumpeter. In concert and studio settings, these collaborations allowed the group to situate their sacred repertoire in innovative artistic contexts. In sum, their activity at this time evolved along two complementary trajectories, one firmly rooted in the communal and religious life of Santu Lussurgiu and the other oriented toward global performance circuits. These dual roles have enabled Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu to preserve their foundational role as ritual singers within their confraternity while affirming their place as ambassadors of Sardinian sacred polyphony on the international stage.

Throughout this phase of their career, the visual representations of Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu in concert posters, album covers, and promotional photographs have consistently reinforced the group's religious identity and their association with the Rosariu confraternity. In nearly all public images, the singers appear wearing the confraternal robe (*abito confraternale*), often facing the camera in solemn poses that underscore their music's spiritual and ceremonial dimensions. When introduced before concerts or in festival programs, presenters frequently highlight their connection to the *Confraternita del Rosario* and, by extension, the sacred life of Santu Lussurgiu. Although their performances may occur in secular venues, the public persona they convey consistently aligns with their confraternity's traditional values, aesthetics, and responsibilities and is framed as the musical expression of a devotional community. According to local customs, certain sacred pieces – particularly the *Miserere* and *Novena*

²⁰ Salis was an educator and cultural organizer. Working with the Unione Italiana Lotta all'Analfabetismo (UNLA), he founded the Centro di Cultura Popolare (Center for folk and popular culture) and the Museo della Tecnologia Contadina (Museum of rural technology) in Santu Lussurgiu and directed these organizations for over fifty years. In 1967, Salis was awarded the UNESCO Reza Pahlavi Prize, which recognized his outstanding contributions to lifelong education. A committed advocate for Sardinian culture, he worked to preserve and promote local traditions. The museum he established houses important artifacts and records of traditional Sardinian life and history, while the Centro di Cultura Popolare became a crucial institution for adult education and cultural engagement in the village.

– are never performed outside ecclesiastical settings, like the church and the confraternal rituals. Singing sacred music in secular contexts thus presents a challenge for the group. One way that they address this is by selecting performance venues with care. Opting for ones perceived as culturally elevated and refined, the group often sings in churches or formal concert halls, rather than open-air stages or popular festival settings. Further, the group sharply separates their sacred and secular repertoires, performing religious songs first and ending with non-religious ones. Reinforcing the division between the two repertoires has been particularly important in international tours and concert events. One of the pivotal moments in the group's history was its involvement in *Sonos 'e Memoria* (sounds of memory). A live event conceived and directed by filmmaker Gianfranco Cabiddu in the mid-1990s, *Sonos 'e Memoria* included projections of archival footage from the Istituto Luce and performances by well-known Sardinian artists like Paolo Fresu, singer Elena Ledda, and pianist Antonello Salis. Singing religious songs in *Sonos 'e Memoria*, *Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu* contributed a religious dimension to the concert's depiction of the island's musical soundscape.²¹ The project was an international success, with a tour that included stops at many European and American festivals and cultural institutions and solidified the ensemble's artistic reputation on two continents.²²

As their international performance career grew, they began to make recordings oriented toward audiences outside of Sardinia and beyond Italy. These recordings were consistently tied to ethnomusicological research, often produced within the framework of scholarly editorial projects and documentation initiatives. In 1992, the group was featured on the landmark French anthology *Sardaigne: Polyphonies de la Semaine Sainte* (Sardinia: Polyphonies of Holy Week), which was released by the Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (the French national center for scientific research) and the Musée de l'Homme and produced by ethnomusicologist Bernard Lortat-Jacob. In 1993, an Italian editorial initiative offered the ensemble its most comprehensive and contextually rooted platform. The Udine-based publisher Nota released *Musica a memoria: Repertori di Tradizione Orale* (music and memory: repertoires of oral tradition). After the decline of the Albatros label – a historic reference point for the publication of orally transmitted music in Italy – Nota took over documenting and disseminating traditional repertoires. Led by Valter Colle, a former student and collaborator of Roberto Leydi, the label emerged as a central player in the new ethnomusicological publishing landscape. Colle brought with him significant experience in audiovisual production and field recording, which became particularly relevant during the transitional period from vinyl to compact disc in the late 1980s and early 1990s. As he explained in an interview:

²¹ Istituto Luce (Institute of the educational film union), founded in 1924 under the Fascist regime, has historically functioned as a central institution for producing, distributing, and archiving educational and propagandistic audiovisual materials in Italy. Today, it operates as part of Cinecittà, managing one of Europe's most extensive audiovisual archives.

²² *Sonos 'e Memoria* was documented in Gianfranco Cabiddu's 2005 film *Passaggi di Tempo: Il Viaggio di Sonos 'e Memoria* (Time passages: the journey of *Sonos 'e Memoria*), which documents the show's genesis, its rehearsal process, and live performances from its tour.

I had a business in audiovisual production, a company that made films and documentaries, so I always had professional audio and video equipment, which I was able to apply in the context of research. [...] In those years, around the late 1980s and early 1990s, the Albatros label had entered a period of crisis. [...] Many colleagues approached me to publish their research, often with funding already secured, because they recognized that I had a production infrastructure and could handle SIAE licensing, graphic design, and printing. [...] I began to discuss publication projects with Roberto Leydi. Then, in 1988, Pietro Sassu arrived in Udine and that sparked a more direct collaboration on specific repertoires. [...] So a sort of network took shape – Leydi, Sassu, Morelli – and gradually also with Leydi’s former students: Ignazio Macchiarella, Nico Staiti, Nicola Scaldaferrì and many others (interview with Valter Colle, November 10, 2022).²³

Sardegna, Confraternite delle Voci (Sardinia, Confraternities of voices) was a four-disc series directed by Pietro Sassu, with each recording featuring the music of a different Sardinian village – Castelsardo, Cuglieri, Orosei, and Santu Lussurgiu. The entry dedicated to Santu Lussurgiu offers a high-fidelity documentation of Su Cuncordu ‘e su Rosariu’s sacred and secular repertoires. Recorded and produced by Valter Colle and Renato Morelli, the disc is accompanied by detailed liner notes authored by Francesco Salis.

Initially released in both cassette and CD formats, *Sardegna. Confraternite delle Voci – Santu Lussurgiu* is divided into two parts; its first eleven tracks contain sacred music, while the last five contain secular music.²⁴ The division between the sacred and secular repertoires is further emphasized in the disc’s liner notes, which are by Pietro Sassu and Francesco Salis. The group does not appear in the album’s cover art but instead features a photograph of other confraternity members raising a statue of Jesus onto a cross during the *s’Ispravamentu* ritual. The visual choice in the album’s production thus emphasizes religious community over the individual identities of the *cuncordu*’s members. The only image of the group appears in the disc’s accompanying booklet – a formal portrait of the four singers facing the camera in their black and white confraternal robes. Sonically, the recording depicts the group’s unique style of singing, which is deeply connected with their identity as members of the Rosariu confraternity (Macchiarella 2014: 7). For years, the disc was the only recording that contained the entire *cuncordu* repertoire of Santu Lussurgiu, and it remains a fundamental introduction to the music for a generation of singers.

²³ [Io avevo un’attività di produzione audiovisiva, una società che produceva filmati e documentari, e quindi ho sempre avuto attrezzatura professionale per l’audio e per il video, che ho potuto applicare anche alla ricerca. [...] In quel periodo lì, fine anni ’80, inizi anni ’90, l’etichetta Albatros era entrata in crisi. [...] Molti colleghi si facevano avanti con me per pubblicare le loro ricerche, magari con finanziamenti già ottenuti, perché riconoscevano in me il fatto che, avendo una struttura produttiva, avevo la capacità di rapportarmi con la SIAE, con la stampa, con la grafica. [...] Abbiamo cominciato a ragionare con Roberto Leydi, poi nel 1988 arrivò Pietro Sassu a Udine e cominciai un confronto più diretto con lui. [...] Così si sono un po’ chiusi dei giochi tra Leydi, Sassu, Morelli, e poi piano piano anche con gli ex allievi di Leydi: Ignazio Macchiarella, Nico Staiti, Nicola Scaldaferrì e tanti altri.]

²⁴ After the 1995 sold out, Nota re-released the album on CD, and the recording is now widely available on streaming music platforms.

FIG. 4. *Sardegna. Confraternita delle Voci – Santu Lussurgiu*, cassette edition. Photo by Diego Pani.

Following the commercial success of the *Confraternita Delle Voci* series, Nota evolved into a major publisher of Italian traditional music. Under Leydi's direction, Nota shifted from releasing CDs with accompanying booklets to publishing a book series, with each volume accompanied by a CD. Each book in the series focuses on a specific kind of musical practice, and the accompanying CD supports the book's analyses with unreleased field recordings. Ignazio Macchiarella's 2009 contribution to the series, *Cantare a Cuncordu: Uno studio a più voci* (Singing *cuncordu*: a study with many voices) is a rich study of *cuncordu* singing in Santu Lussurgiu and the legacy of Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu activity. Its CD includes a new recording by the group.²⁵

Ignazio Macchiarella, a Sicilian ethnomusicologist, student of Roberto Leydi and close collaborator of Pietro Sassu, already knew the singers of Santu Lussurgiu and had spent several periods in the village (he was one of the "those of '91," from the 1991 conference). In 2014 he arrived in Sardinia as a researcher at the University of Cagliari (he is now a full professor of ethnomusicology at the same university), choosing to live between the Sardinian capital and Santu Lussurgiu to pursue dedicated fieldwork with the singers of Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu, increasingly becoming a villager himself. *Cantare a Cuncordu* illustrates Macchiarella's approach to research on *cuncordu* singing, using techniques of

²⁵ Shortly after the release of the *Confraternita delle Voci* series, Ignazio Macchiarella reviewed the collection, noting that it «document[s] four living musical traditions connected with different villages among the most representative of the whole Island» (Macchiarella 1997). His remarks emphasize how the series framed these communities – Castelsardo, Orosei, Cuglieri, and Santu Lussurgiu – as exemplary cases of Sardinian multipart singing.

dialogic writing shared with the singers of Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu. The book's title page lists Macchiarella as editor and names both him and the members of the *cuncordu* as co-authors, emphasizing the dialogic nature of the research, the central role of the singers in it, and the decade of collaborative work that led to its publication. It treats the music as a living tradition – structured through codified rules of comportment, performance, and stylistic canons – and as a dynamic field of negotiation shaped by generational transmission, media exposure, and changing ritual ecologies. Particularly noteworthy here is Macchiarella's emphasis on the internal discourse among the singers, whose interpretations of local cultural memory and ideas about propriety and musical excellence are the emic framework that defines multipart singing in the group. The singers' contributions extend well beyond descriptions of local ritual practices and transmission processes: they also reflect on their experiences of performing internationally, their relationships with musicians from other traditions, and their long-standing engagement with Italian and international ethnomusicologists. These perspectives allow the book to depict *cuncordu* not simply as a village-based devotional practice but as an emergent tradition negotiated within broader cultural circuits. The book's accompanying CD was conceived as a complement to the group's 1995 debut album. It presents new recordings, including a restored version of *Te Deum*. In the past, this piece had been part of the *Ordinarium Missae* but had disappeared from the religious repertoire in Santu Lussurgiu, and its inclusion in this second CD expands the sonic record of the village's sacred repertoire already started with the 1995 recording. Also noteworthy are the *Gosos of Don Bosco*, conceived as a new "composition" in the traditional form of *Gosos* (devotional songs dedicated to saints and widely sung in Sardinia), here honoring a Saint, Don Bosco, particularly venerated in Santu Lussurgiu, where a Salesian order was active from 1906 to 1972. On the secular side, the disc includes interpretations of *Istudiantina*, *Acchetuzzedda*, and *Pastorina*, each performed with alternate poetic texts, thereby highlighting the elasticity of form and the interpretative plurality of the local secular tradition. As Ignazio Macchiarella notes, he did not intervene in the production of the CD, leaving the singers with full responsibility for its content (Macchiarella 2009: 26).²⁶

From village ritual practitioners to internationally recognized performing artists, the many roles that Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu has played have profoundly shaped their status in Santu Lussurgiu. Their international visibility – gained through concert tours, collaborations with well-known artists, and participation in prestigious festivals – has elevated the singers' prestige within the village itself, positioning them as both cultural ambassadors and local authorities. This elevated status has, in turn, fostered the engagement of younger generations with the Rosariu Confraternity, who view the

²⁶ Su Rosariu's approach to recording inspired a range of self-produced discs by groups across Sardinia. In 2015, Su Cuncordu de Sette Dolores, a Lussurgese group associated with the Sette Dolores confraternity, released a self-produced album that was clearly modeled on the older group's recording. Titled *Voci della tradizione: Canti liturgici e profani di tradizione orale* (voices of the tradition: sacred and secular traditional songs) also differentiates the two repertoires, the back cover graphics dividing the list of songs between *Il Sacro* (the sacred) and *Il Profano* (the secular).

ensemble not only as custodians of tradition but also as models of artistic and moral authority. Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu first came to prominence through the lens of ethnomusicological inquiry, which framed their practices within a narrative of preservation and scholarly interest. However, the ensemble soon encountered the favors of the international world music scene, a context in which traditional musics are not only performed but actively mediated, packaged, and circulated for global audiences. As Jocelyne Guilbault (1997) notes, world music is best understood not as a genre but as a «marketing classification and ideological construct» that situates non-Western musics within the logics of global distribution, often accompanied by discourses of authenticity and exoticism (1997: 33). In this framework, local musics «are marketed, distributed, and frequently accompanied by an ethnographic and educational discourse», which transforms their meaning and repositions them within both global and local hierarchies (1997: 33). This reframing does not occur in a vacuum; instead, it leads to a redefinition of legitimacy and prestige at the local level, as communities respond to how their traditions are represented and consumed externally. In the case of Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu, this dynamic has contributed to the symbolic authority they hold within the village, while also shaping expectations around performance, decorum, and an idea of identity that is simultaneously rooted in confraternal devotion and oriented toward external recognition. Their identity as singers is no longer defined solely by local ritual functions, but increasingly by their ability to embody a form of cultural authenticity that resonates with both community values and global imaginaries of tradition. As such, their presence becomes emblematic of a broader negotiation between belonging and representation, between continuity and the mediatized self. Building on this legacy, a younger generation of singers – raised within the sonic and ethical framework established by Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu – is now gradually carrying the torch, embracing the confraternal tradition while navigating its transmission in a changing cultural landscape.

SU CUNCORDU SOS TZOVANOS DE SU ROSARIU: MUSIC LEARNING, MEDIATIZATION AND CANON FORMATION

In recent years, a new generation of singers has assumed an increasingly vital role in the vocal practices of the Rosariu confraternity. Among them is my thirty-one-year-old nephew, Antonio Meloni, who was the young singer discussed in the ethnographic vignette that opened this article. Today, he and three close companions from the Rosariu confraternity – Nicola Migheli (thirty-five), Sergio Scalas (thirty-seven), and Tonio Cadau (forty-five) – form *Su Cuncordu Sos Tzovanos de su Rosariu* (The young singers of the Rosary confraternity). All four have grown up in the confraternal milieu, absorbing its rituals, musical practice, and values from an early age. For two of them, multipart singing is also a matter of family legacy: Nicola is the son of Antonio Migheli, long-time 'oghe of Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu, and Tonio is the son of Paolo Cadau, a long-standing confraternity member and occasional *bassu* singer. Their involvement in the lay religious

group is neither occasional nor symbolic. Each is an active confraternity member, participating in processions, masses, and the many devotional and convivial events that make up its calendar.

For several years, Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu and Su Cuncordu Sos Zovanos de su Rosariu performed side by side during the Holy Week rites. The 2019 edition was particularly significant, as it marked the last time Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu appeared in its full historical formation, with Giovanni Ardu still singing the *bassu* part before his untimely passing in 2020. On that occasion, both ensembles sang with Ardu, since Tonio Cadau of Su Cuncordu Sos Zovanos de su Rosariu was absent from the rites. The videos I recorded that year vividly capture the exchange and proximity between the two choirs as they alternated at different stations of the Good Friday procession ([video 1 and 2](#)). However, through consistent practice and accumulated vocal experience, Su Cuncordu Sos Zovanos de su Rosariu has since been increasingly acknowledged as the generational successor to Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu in the living transmission of the tradition. Since 2020, they have been entrusted with performing the central Holy Week rituals of *s'Incravamentu* and *s'Isravamentu*, assuming the principal role of ritual singers – a responsibility symbolically and practically passed down to them by Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu.

FIG. 5. *Su Cuncordu Sos Zovanos de su Rosariu* singing during the 2023 Holy Week rituals. Photo by Diego Pani.

Today, his peers recognize Antonio as an expert singer within the Rosariu Confraternity and the wider village community. As a young singer, Antonio frequently used Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu's 1995 recording as a critical guide to the tradition, a sonic model that shaped his aesthetic expectation and performance style. When he began his journey in multipart singing, he listened to the recording repeatedly, closely imitating its vocal style

and internalizing its interpretative approach. As he explained during our interviews, he returned to that recording many times in the early stages of his training. For him, the very act of recording represents a gesture of generosity for which he expresses profound gratitude toward the elder singers of Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu.

The greatest merit of Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu was first and foremost their decision to take up the tradition of cantu a *cuncordu* and to record it the way they did. This made it possible for many young people to listen to it – more often, and with more attention to each individual part. I can speak for myself: as I said, I began by singing along with the recording, and many others did the same. This allows you to refine your skills. Even now, we still rely on their recordings – whether on YouTube or elsewhere – especially when we're unsure about a particular passage. When you have a doubt about a song, you go back to their recordings (Interview with Antonio Meloni, March 18, 2023).²⁷

For Antonio, like me, that particular recording served as both a pedagogical device and a symbolic artifact, crystallizing a particular moment in the history of the singers of the Rosariu confraternity and enabling its transmission across generational lines. Over time, though, his initial, highly mediated relationship with the tradition became less important for learning the music than face-to-face interactions with other vocalists, which have occurred in a variety of social contexts and gradually allowed him to be included in the community of local singers. These experiences ranged from the tryouts with various groups to first-hand experiences singing with senior vocalists. Here, Antonio moved from a basic understanding of a fixed repertoire to a deeper understanding of the tradition's singing techniques, lyrics, and historical styles, which are often associated with well-known singers of the past. Participating in confraternal events, village festivals like carnival, and occasional convivial gatherings with other singers, he developed a singing proficiency beyond the examples furnished by the recordings.²⁸

Antonio's experience of learning the tradition is not unique. For many singers of his generation, the 1995 recording served as a gateway to understanding *cuncordu* singing. This mediated approach to listening and learning the roles within the *cuncordu* – training the ear to distinguish voices, rehearsing alone before joining others – also resonates with my own memories. As a child, I too began to approach singing timidly, trying to replicate

²⁷ [Il merito più grande che ha Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu è stato innanzitutto aver ripreso in mano tutto quello che riguarda il canto a *cuncordu*, registrare come hanno registrato, perché questo ha permesso a molti giovani di poterlo ascoltare, di più e di poterlo ascoltare più attentamente nelle varie parti. Io parlo per me, come ho detto, io ho iniziato appunto cantando sul cd, come me tanti altri. Questo ti permette di perfezionarsi perché anche noi inizialmente, ma ci capita tuttora, adesso, magari tramite YouTube, comunque riprendendo sempre le tracce registrate da loro, quando hai un dubbio, quando si ha un dubbio qualsiasi appunto su un canto vai a riprendere i canti registrati da Su Cuncordu].

²⁸ A case in point is *s'istudiantina*, a metrical and melodic framework traditionally used to accommodate a wide variety of secular lyrics drawn from the local repertoire. While listeners familiar only with the 1995 recording may associate the piece with a single text – the one chosen for that particular recording – experienced singers often know and perform multiple alternate versions, some of which are rare and have circulated exclusively through oral transmission. In this context, textual competence – alongside vocal technique – emerges as a key marker of expertise, highlighting the depth and variability of oral knowledge embedded in the tradition.

one of the four parts I heard on those recordings, within the solitude of my bedroom. Unlike me, however, Antonio – more attentive and committed to developing as a singer – was soon admitted into the oral dimension of the tradition. The transition from solitary repetition of a recorded model to live performance with others marks an important threshold: the moment one begins to navigate the *cuncordu* world with its complex landscape of personal styles, aesthetics, and rules. In this space, learning to sing means more than simply reproducing a part – it requires the ability to grasp the implicit logics that shape interaction. Each singer must learn to move within a web of nuances, tensions, and expressive choices, following a specific *tràgiu*, a personal sonic trajectory internalized through repeated practice and listening, a polysemic concept that contributes to defining the specificity of a local musical practice and encompasses not only formal and technical elements, but also the stylistic manners, contextual meanings, and performative values embedded within the tradition. (Macchiarella 2021). Mastery lies not in reproducing a fixed model, but in understanding how to adapt, modulate, and respond – how to sing with others without erasing one’s voice or rigidly clinging to any single recorded version. The recording remains and continues to anchor the canonized form of the repertoire, yet beyond it opens the living world of tradition, where singers must find their path by listening, breathing together, and interpreting what lies between voices.

FIG. 6. Holy Week 2016. My nephew Antonio makes his debut alongside the elder singers of Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu, replacing Mario Corona during the performance of the *Miserere* in the Good Friday procession. In the background, various people listen to the performance; among them is ethnomusicologist Ignazio Macchiarella. Photo by Diego Pani.

In this sense, the recording stands as a clear example of what Lundberg, Malm, and Ronström (2003) describe as primary mediatization, reflecting Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu's agency in shaping the multipart singing canon within the community. As Macchiarella (2009: 56) has noted, for many singers in Santu Lussurgiu the 1995 recording defines both the village's repertoire and the local discourse on multipart singing. For beginners, its tracks indicate how to sing properly, and its division between the sacred and profane repertoires indicates which should be sung in which contexts. Whether a singer encounters the album as a CD, a cassette, or its seemingly immaterial form as a collection of MP3s, the disc detaches the music from its context of oral performance proper. Endlessly available for repeated listening, it presents a fixed, canonized form of the *cuncordu* multipart singing repertoire. While face-to-face performance ultimately comes to replace the disc as the primary site of music learning, it remains an important part of their musical experience.

As Rosenberg (2002) has argued, key recordings of traditional music do not merely document songs but canonize specific versions, reinforcing stylistic consistency across generations. Through primary mediatization, such recordings thus become authoritative references, institutionalizing selected styles and repertoires. In this context, I would suggest that *su Rosariu's* 1995 recording operates as I would call a mediatized canon, one that is produced through the materiality, permanence, and pedagogical efficacy of the recording and continues to shape how young singers like Antonio learn, embody, and perpetuate their tradition.

The sustained presence of ethnomusicologists in Santu Lussurgiu has significantly influenced processes of canon formation. The younger singers of Su Cuncordu Sos Zovanos de su Rosariu grew up in a context where multipart singing was firmly embedded in the cultural life of confraternal and village communities, but also consistently observed and studied by outsiders. Among these scholars, Ignazio Macchiarella stands out: since the beginning of his research, he has spent part of each year residing in the village – a practice he continues to this day. His long-term engagement has contributed to shaping local perceptions of multipart singing not only as a community practice but also as a form of musical heritage valued by a wider, translocal network of scholars and musicians. At the same time, as Macchiarella himself observes, the “secondary orality” of Santu Lussurgiu's *cuncordu* tradition illustrates how recording has become integral to the transmission of multipart singing, guiding stylistic expectations, technical refinement, and even conceptions of authenticity (Macchiarella 2012: 3) – a concept that directly draws from Walter Ong's seminal theory of mediated orality. Ong defined secondary orality as «the orality of telephones, radio, and television, which depends on writing and print for its existence [...] essentially a more deliberate and self-conscious orality» (Ong 1982: 136). As Ong noted, secondary orality is more reflexive and formalized than primary orality – a characteristic that is evident in the ways younger singers in Santu Lussurgiu engage with recorded materials to guide their learning and shape their sonic aesthetic. In this context, the repeated listening to, and emulation of, recorded performances alters the nature of tradition itself, producing a form of deliberate continuity anchored in the authority of technologically mediated

exemplars, in this case, the example of Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu. In this context, recordings do not merely document local practices but become foundational tools for transmission, rehearsal, and aesthetic modeling. This dynamic aligns with Rosenberg's analysis of Don Messer's media repertoire, in which the repeated circulation of recorded performances contributes to the formation of a selectively constructed canon – anchoring perceptions of authenticity and shaping the expectations of both performers and audiences (Rosenberg 2002: 204). As noted in previous sections, the 1995 *Confraternita delle Voci* CD recording has functioned precisely this way, serving as both archive and template. The authority of Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu, mediated through this recording and extended through scholarly and public visibility, has deeply influenced the next generation of singers.

In Santu Lussurgiu, the 1995 recording of Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu represents what may be called a mediated canon – a body of repertoire that becomes fixed and authoritative through its circulation in recorded form. The introduction of such recordings into an oral context has profoundly reshaped the conditions of transmission. Whether produced by ethnomusicologists, local researchers, or the singers themselves, these recordings stabilize repertoires and come to function as canonical markers within the community. Yet the act of recording is never neutral: by documenting traditions, scholars and researchers also contribute to their capitalization, endowing them with new forms of legitimacy and cultural value. The history of these recordings ties the singers from Su Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu closely to the development of ethnomusicological research in Italy – from the *Autunno Musicale* in Como and the pioneering work of Roberto Leydi, to the audiovisual projects carried out by Renato Morelli, and above all, the profound collaboration and fraternal friendship with Pietro Sassu. This trajectory extends further through the partnership with Ignazio Macchiarella, which culminated – among many other outputs (including numerous articles, conferences, and concerts) – in the publication of *A Cuncordu*, a volume conceived as a dialogue between singers and the ethnomusicologist. These moments mark the stages of a musical path rooted in oral tradition but, from its very beginnings in the late 1970s, directly connected to and in dialogue with the Italian school of ethnomusicology. It is precisely within this nexus that the mediated canon of 1995 must be situated, underlining the particularly influential place ethnomusicology occupies within the very oral traditions it seeks to study.

MULTIMEDIA CONTENTS

VIDEO

AVAILABLE AT: [HTTPS://WWW.SOUNDETHNOGRAPHIES.IT/IT/PANI-2025-MULTIMEDIA/](https://www.soundethnographies.it/it/pani-2025-multimedia/)

Video 1. Cuncordu 'e su Rosariu – *Miserere* (Holy Week 2019) [02:04].

Video 2. Cuncordu Sos Zovanos de su Rosariu – *Miserere* (Holy Week 2019) [01:57].

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